

Chemical, biocidal and pharmacological aspects of *Origanum* species : A brief review

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Abstract : The review is based on chemical, biocidal and pharmacological approach of *Origanum* species. Almost all *Origanum* species have carvacrol as major compound. Other major compounds such as thymol, γ -terpinene, *p*-cymene, linalool, terpinen-4-ol, germacrene-D, β -caryophyllene, myrcene etc. are reported in *Origanum* species. Flavonoids, phenolic acids, glycosides, glycolipids, and phospholipids are also reported in *Origanum* species. The extract of *Origanum* species have been found to exhibit antifungal, antibacterial, antioxidant, antimalarial, inhibition action etc.

Keywords : *Origanum*, review, chemistry, pharmacology, biocidal activity.

Introduction

Essential oils, produced by the plants secondary metabolism, are complex mixtures of low molecular weight terpenes¹. Their environmental function is related to defense against phytophagous insects and/or attraction of pollinators, as well as to intra- or inter-specific allelopathic phenomena².

Origanum is a genus of herbaceous perennials and sub shrubs in the family *Lamiaceae*, native to Europe, North Africa, and much of temperate Asia, where they are found in open or mountainous habitats. *Origanum* is an important multipurpose medicinal plant which belongs to the family *Lamiaceae*, tribe Mentheae and comprises of 42 species and 18 hybrids widely distributed in Eurasia and North Africa^{3,4}. It is native to the mountainous parts of Mediterranean region of Europe and Asia. The genus *Origanum* has been divided into 10 sections. Six subspecies have been recognized within *O. vulgare* L. based on differences in indumentum, number of sessile glands on leaves, bracts and calyces, and in size and colour of bracts and flowers : subsp. *vulgare*, subsp. *glandulosum* (Desfontaines) Ietswaart, subsp. *gracile* (Koch) Ietswaart, subsp. *hirtum* (Link) Ietswaart, subsp. *viridulum* (Martrin-Donos) Nyman and subsp. *virens* (Hoffmannsegg and Link) Ietswaart.

Oregano has purple flowers and spade-shaped, olive-green leaves. It is a perennial⁵ although it is grown as an annual in colder climates, as it often does not survive the winter months^{6,7}. *Oregano* is planted in early spring, the plants being spaced 30 cm (12 in) apart in fairly dry soil, with full sun. It prefers a hot, relatively dry climate. *Oregano* is a perennial herb, growing from 20–80 cm tall, with opposite leaves 1–4 cm long. *Oregano* will grow in a pH range between 6.0 (mildly acidic) and 9.0 (strongly alkaline) with a preferred range between 6.0 and 8.0. The flowers are purple, 3–4 mm long, produced in erect spikes. It is sometimes called wild marjoram, and its close relative *O. majorana* is known as sweet marjoram. Many subspecies and strains of *Oregano* have been developed by humans over centuries for their unique flavors or other characteristics. Tastes range from spicy or astringent to more complicated and sweet. Simple *Oregano* sold in garden stores as *O. vulgare* may have a bland taste and larger, less dense leaves, and is not considered the best for culinary uses. It can pollinate other more sophisticated strains, but the offspring are rarely better in quality. The genus *Origanum* contains two important aromatic plants with different sensorial qualities, marjoram (*Origanum majorana* L.) and *Oregano* (*Origanum* sp.,

Chemical composition of <i>Origanum</i> species			
Species/Subspecies	Plant part used/Extract	Major compounds isolated	Ref. No.
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Leaf and flower essential oil	Thymol, <i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene and 1-octen-3-ol	32
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>hirtum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, thymol, <i>p</i> -cymene and γ -terpinene	33
<i>O. syriacum</i> ssp. <i>sinaicum</i>	Essential oil	Thymol, γ -terpinene and <i>p</i> -cymene	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	β -Caryophyllene, caryophyllene oxide	34
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene	35
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>viride</i>	Aerial part bloom stage essential oil	Thymol, γ -terpinene, β -pinene, 3-octanone, carvacrol, sabinene, α -pinene	36
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. subsp. <i>viride</i> (Boiss.) Hayek	Aerial part essential oil	<i>o</i> -Cymene, linalyl propanoate, linalool, β -myrcene, α -pinene limonene	37
<i>O. glandulosum</i> (Desf.)	Essential oil	Thymol, carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene and γ -terpinene	38
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	γ -Terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene, linalool and thymol	39
<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol	40
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, phenol	44
<i>O. ramonense</i> Danin	Essential oil	Enantiomers (<i>E</i>)- and (<i>Z</i>)-sabinene hydrate	45
<i>O. dayi</i> Post		and of (<i>E</i>)- and (<i>Z</i>)-sabinene hydrate acetate	
<i>O. majorana</i> L.			
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. <i>vulgare</i>			
<i>O. syriacum</i> L. ssp. <i>syriacum</i>			
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. <i>vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Spathulenol, caryophyllene oxide, α -terpeneol, 1,8-cineol, β -caryophyllene, terpenin-4-ol	46
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil in flowering stage	Sabinene, β -ocimene, β -caryophyllene, germacrene-D	47
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Leaves essential oil, irradiation by γ -rays non-irradiated control sample oil	Myrcene, <i>p</i> -cymene, carvacryl methyl ether and 1-borneol changes were observed for carvacrol and thymol	48
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. <i>hirtum</i>	Leaves essential oil	Carvacrol, linalool, β -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene	49
<i>O. majorana</i>	Essential oil	Sabinyl-chemotype	50
<i>O. dubium</i>		Linalool-chemotype	
<i>O. onites</i>		Linalool-chemotype	
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Linalool	51
	locality variation	Thymol	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil aerial parts	Linalool, myrcene, β -caryophyllene, germacrene-D, terpinen-4-ol	52
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. <i>hirtum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol	53
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. <i>hirtum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol	54
subsp. <i>gracile</i>		γ -Caryophyllene, germacrene-D	
subsp. <i>viridewere</i>		Terpinen-4-ol, germacrene-D	
subsp. <i>vulgare</i>		Terpinen-4-ol, β -caryophyllene germacrene-D	
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. <i>hirtum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol and thymol	55
<i>O. syriacum</i> var. <i>bevanii</i>		Carvacrol and thymol	
<i>O. majorana</i>	Two chemotype	Carvacrol	
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>		Carvacrol	

<i>O. onites</i>		Carvacrol type and linalool type	
<i>O. x applii</i> (Domin) Boros	Essential oil chemotype O.A.1030, O.A.1031 O.A.1032	Thymol, linalyl acetate, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene, terpinen-4-ol, sabinene	56
<i>O. majorana</i>	Leaf extract	Phenolic compounds (gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, catechin, gentisic acid, chlorogenic acid, vanillic acid, syringic acid, caffeic acid, epicatechin, benzoic acid)	58
<i>O. husnucanbaseri</i>	Essential oil	Borneol, α -terpineol, <i>trans</i> -sabinene	59
<i>O. hypericifolium</i> O. Schwartz and P. H. Davis	Aerial part essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, carvacrol, γ -terpinene	60
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Extract	Flavonoids : quercetin glucoside, apigenin glucoside Phenolics : ferulic acid, rosmarinic acid, <i>p</i> -coumarin, caffeic acid	61
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, thymol, carvacrol	62
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil chemotype Champawat region, Kilbury, Kumaun Hills	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpinene, thymol, carvacrol, linalool, bornyl acetate, γ -caryophyllene, germacrene-D	63
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, camphene, γ -terpinene, thymol, carvacrol	64
<i>O. vulgare</i> spp. vulgare	Essential oil end of flowering stage	Sabinene, (<i>Z</i>)- β -ocimene, γ -terpinene, (<i>E</i>)- β -ocimene, δ -cadinene, thymol, <i>cis</i> -sabinene hydrate, β -caryophyllene, terpinen-4-ol, germacrene-D	65
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, β -terpineol, methyl carvacrol	66
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. gracile	Essential oil	Sabinene, germacrene-D, β -ocimene,	67
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. viren		β -caryophyllene	
<i>O. tythanthus</i> Gontsch.	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpineol, thymol, carvacrol	68
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. viridulum	Essential oil	Thymol	69
<i>O. libanoticum</i> Boiss		Methyl thymol	
<i>O. syriacum</i> L.		Carvacrol	
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Aerial part essential oil	γ -Muurolene, δ -cadinene, elemol	70
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Aerial part extracted with MeOH-H ₂ O (3 : 1)	Flavonoids	71
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum (Link)	Essential oil	Terpenic and sesquiterpenic hydrocarbons	72
Ietswaart (syn. <i>O. heracleoticum</i>)			
<i>Oregano</i> species 'Cordobes' Criollo, Mendocino Compacto	Essential oil	Thymol, <i>trans</i> -sabinene hydrate, terpinen- 4-ol, α -terpinene γ -Terpinene, limonene	73
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Thymol chemotype	74
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpinene, thymol, carvacrol	77
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. subsp. hirtum Ietswaart	Essential oil	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, α -terpinene	78
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum (Link) Ietswaart	Essential oil	Carvacrol	79
<i>O. floribundum</i>	Essential oil, dry leaves	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene, thymol, thymol-methyl ether	80

<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. glandulosum		Thymol, carvacrol-methylether, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene, carvacrol	
<i>O. hypericifolium</i> O. Schwartz and P. H. Davis	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, carvacrol, thymol, γ -terpinene	81
<i>O. syriacum</i>	Essential oil	Thymol, carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene	82
<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol, carvone, limonene, thymol	83
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Ethanol and water extract (4 : 1)	Isovanillic acid, vanillic acid, quercetin, rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid, protocatechuic acid	84
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Supercritical CO ₂ extraction of essential oil	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, β -terpinene, terpinene-4-ol, thymol	85
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. hirtum	Essential oil	Carvacrol	86
<i>Origanum x dolichosiphon</i> P. H. Davis	Essential oil	Bicyclogermacrene, β -caryophyllene, germacrene-D	87
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol and thymol	88
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum	Essential oil	Carvacrol	89
<i>O. majorana</i>	Essential oil	Thymol, carvacrol, γ -terpinene and <i>p</i> -cymene	90
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum	Essential oil	Terpinen-4-ol, <i>cis</i> -sabinene hydrate, <i>p</i> -cymene, sabinene, <i>trans</i> -sabinene hydrate and α -terpineol	
<i>Origanum heracleoticum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, thymol and β -phellandrene	91
<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil	Thymol	92
<i>O. majorana</i> L. syn.	Essential oil	Carvacrol/	93
<i>O. majorana hortensis</i> Moench	Chemotype	Thymol type	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. hirtum	Essential oil	Carvacrol, γ -terpinene, thymol, <i>p</i> -cymene	94
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. vulgare		<i>p</i> -Cymene, caryophyllene oxide, sabinene, γ -terpinene, thymol, spathulenol	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Trace elements and essential oil composition	95
<i>O. onites</i>	Lipids and essential oil	Glycolipids, phospholipids, β -sitosterol carvacrol, thymol, γ -terpinene	96
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. virens (Hoffm. et Link) Ietswaart	Essential oil flowering stage, CO ₂ extraction- hydrodistilled	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpinene, linalool, carvacrol, thymol, α -terpinenol, β -caryophyllene	97
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. virens (Hoffm. et Link) Ietswaart	Essential oil flowering stage CO ₂ extraction- hydrodistilled	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpinene, linalool, carvacrol, thymol, α -terpinenol with increase of bract size decrease in concentration of <i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene decrease in bract size, an increase in concentration of linalool, α -terpineol, thymol and phenol derivatives	98
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene	99
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Spathulenol, γ -caryophyllene, caryophyllene oxide, 1,8-cineol, α -terpineol, terpinen-4-ol	101
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. hirtum	Essential oil	Carvacrol and thymol	107
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. subsp. glandulosum	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, thymol, γ -terpinene and carvacrol	108

<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, γ -fenchyl alcohol, thymol and γ -terpinene	109
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Hydro-distillation	<i>p</i> -Cymene	110
<i>O. syriacum</i> L. var. <i>bevanii</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol	111
	MeOH extracts	Polar and nonpolar phenolics	
<i>O. heracleoticum</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol	112
<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol	113
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol	
<i>O. heracleoticum</i>	Solvent extract (ether)	Flavonoids, rosmarinic acid	114
<i>O. saccatum</i> L.	Aerial part, essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene-8-ol and carvacrol	116
<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil	Carvacrol, thymol, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene, α -terpinene,	117
	extract	α -pinene, phenolic compounds rosmarinic acid and acecetin	
<i>O. syriacum</i> L.	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, phenolic monoterpenes, γ -terpinene	118
<i>Oregano</i> species	Essential oil	Carvacrol, thymol, borneol, thymoquinone	119
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>virens</i>	Essential oil	Phytomorphological and genotype variation	120
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>viridulum</i>			
<i>O. glandulosum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, γ -terpinene, thymol	121
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Thymol, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene, carvacrol	122
	of flowering plant		
	and non-flowering plants		
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. <i>vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Carvomenthol, terpinolene, thymol, γ -terpinene	125
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil mixed with	Thymol, carvacrol, 1,8-cineole, α -pinene,	126
	other oil	<i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene	
<i>O. compactum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, thymol, <i>p</i> -cymene	128
<i>O. glandulosum</i>	Essential oil	Thymol, carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, γ -terpinene	129
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Aerial part	Salvianolic acid A, salvianolic acid C,	130
	ethanol extract	lithospermic acid, apigenin 7- <i>O</i> - β -D-glucuronide, apigenin 7- <i>O</i> - β -D-(6''-methyl)glucuronide, luteolin, luteolin 7- <i>O</i> - β -D-glucopyranoside, luteolin 7- <i>O</i> - β -D-glucuronide, luteolin 7- <i>O</i> - β -D-xylopyranoside	
<i>O. onites</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, linalool, <i>p</i> -cymene	131
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>hirtum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene	132
<i>O. majorana</i> L.	Essential oil	Terpinen-4-ol, <i>cis</i> -sabinene hydrate, linalyl acetate, <i>trans</i> -sabinene hydrate, linalool, β -terpinene carvacrol	133
<i>O. majorana</i> L.		<i>cis</i> -sabinene hydrate	
<i>Origanum x majoricum</i> Cambess.		<i>cis</i> -Sabinene hydrate, terpinen-4-ol, linalyl acetate, <i>trans</i> -sabinene hydrate, linalool, carvacrol, β -terpinene	
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>hirtum</i>	Essential oil	<i>p</i> -Cymene, thymol	134
<i>O. onites</i>		Carvacrol, sabinene, myrcene, γ -terpinene, borneol	
<i>Origanum x majoricum</i> Cambessedes	Essential oil	<i>trans</i> -Sabinene hydrate, carvacrol, sabinene, γ -terpinene and terpinen-4-ol	135
<i>Origanum x intercedens</i> Rechingen		Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, β -terpinene and myrcene	
<i>O. x minoanum</i>		Carvacrol, γ -terpinene and <i>p</i> -cymene	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. <i>vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Sabinene, β -ocimene, (<i>E</i>)- β -caryophyllene, germacrene-D, linalool, caryophyllene oxide, spathulenol	136

<i>O. cordifolium</i> Monbret et. Aucher	Essential oil	α -Terpineol, carvacrol, γ -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene	137
<i>O. bastetanum</i> Soc.	Essential oil	β -Terpinene, thymol, <i>p</i> -cymene, β -caryophyllene	138
<i>O. compactum</i>	Essential oil	γ -Terpinene, carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, linalool	139
<i>O. dictamnus</i>		Linalool, terpinen-4-ol	
<i>O. dubium</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene, β -terpinene	
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene	
<i>O. onites</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene, β -terpinene	
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>hirtum</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene, β -terpinene	
<i>O. dayi</i> Post	Essential oil	1,8-Cineole, terpinen-4-ol, α -terpineol	140
<i>O. elongatum</i> Emberger et. Maire	Essential oil	Carvacrol, β -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene, linalool	141
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>gracile</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol type	142
<i>O. acutidens</i>	(chemotypes)	Carvacrol type	
<i>O. hypericifolium</i>		Thymol type	
<i>O. bargyli</i>		Carvacrol type	
<i>O. saccatum</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene type	
<i>O. solymicum</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene/carcacrol, thymol type	
<i>O. leptocladum</i>		Thymol/carcacrol type	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. subsp. <i>hirtum</i> (Link) Ietswaart	Essential oil	Thymol, β -terpinene, <i>p</i> -cymene	143
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene	144
<i>O. vulgare</i> x <i>O. majorana</i>	Essential oil	<i>cis</i> -Sabinene hydrate	145
<i>O. syriacum</i> ssp. <i>syriacum</i>	(temperature influence)	Carvacrol	
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>	Essential oil	Carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene	146
<i>O. majorana</i> L.	Essential oil	Linalyl acetate, sabinene, γ -terpinene, <i>cis</i> -sabinene hydrate	147
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.		<i>cis</i> -piperitol, γ -terpineol, <i>p</i> -cymene	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. subsp. <i>viride</i> (Boiss.) Hayek		β -Caryophyllene, germacrene-D, <i>trans</i> -sabinene hydrate, sabinene, γ -humulene, valencene and (<i>E</i>)- δ -ocimene, linalyl acetate, sabinene, caryophyllene, γ -terpinene, β -caryophyllene oxide, germacrene-D, (<i>E</i>)- δ -ocimene, (<i>Z</i>)- δ -ocimene and β -elemene	
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Terpinen-4-ol, carvacrol, thymol, γ -terpinene	148
<i>O. ehrenbergii</i> Boiss	Essential oil	Thymol, <i>p</i> -cymene	149
<i>O. syriacum</i> L.		Thymol, carvacrol	
<i>O. vulgare</i>		<i>trans</i> -Sabinene hydrate, thymol, carvacrol	
<i>O. Majorana</i> O. (minutiflorum) onites	Essential oil	Carvacrol	150
<i>O. syriacum</i> var. <i>bevanii</i>			
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>hirtum</i>			
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>vulgare</i>			
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>gracile</i>		Caryophyllene	
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. <i>vulgare</i>		<i>p</i> -Cymene	
<i>O. sipyleum</i>		Terpinene	
<i>O. onites</i> , <i>O. gracile</i>		Linalool	
<i>Oregano vulgare</i> L. ssp.	Ethanol extracts	Rosmarinic acid luteolin, apigenin, flavonol, quercetin	151

(contd.)

hirtum (Greek oregano)	Acetone extracts		
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Chemotype I	<i>p</i> -Cymene, γ -terpinene, thymol, carvacrol	152
	Chemotype II	Thymol, caryophyllene oxide, aliphatic hydrocarbons	
	Chemotype III	Linalool, thymol, carvacrol, β -caryophyllene, germacrene-D	
	Chemotype IV	Linalool, bornyl acetate, β -caryophyllene, germacrene-D, bicyclogermacrene, elemol	
<i>O. majorana</i>	Essential oil	4-Terpinene, γ -terpinene, α -terpinene and sabinene	154
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Thymol and carvacrol	155
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Sabinene, 1,8-cineole, caryophyllene oxide, (<i>E</i>)- β -caryophyllene, <i>p</i> -cymene, α -terpineol and germacrene-D	157
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum	Essential oil	Carvacrol/thymol, phenolic compounds	158
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. vulgare	Essential oil high altitude	Thymol	159
	Essential oil low altitude	Carvacrol	
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. hirtum	Essential oil	Carvacrol	160

Biocidal and pharmacological properties of *Origanum* species

Species/Subspecies	Plant part used/Extract	Major compounds isolated	Ref. No.
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Food and flavour	32
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Anti-oxidative and anti-genotoxic	34
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil in flowering	Antifungal	41
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antioxidant	42
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	EtOH extracts	Antioxidant	43
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antioxidant	44
<i>Oregano</i>	Essential oil	Antioxidant	57
<i>O. majorana</i>	Leaves extract	Antioxidant	58
<i>O. husnucanbaseri</i>	Essential oil	Antibacterial	59
<i>O. hypericifolium</i>	Aerial part	Antioxidant, antibacterial	60
O. Schwartz and P. H. Davis	Essential oil		
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Extract	Antioxidant	61
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antifungal	62
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antimalarial	64
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial, antioxidant	66
<i>O. tythanthum</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial earlier work	68
<i>Oregano</i> species 'Cordobes', Criollo, Mendocino Compacto	Essential oil	Radical scavenging activity and antioxidant activity	73
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antifungal	75
<i>Oregano (O. vulgare)</i> L.	Extract	Lipid peroxidation and antioxidant in induced carcinogenesis	76
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Antifungal activity	77
<i>O. hypericifolium</i>	Essential oil	Antifungal activity	81
O. Schwartz and P. H. Davis			
<i>O. syriacum</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial activity	82

<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil	Inhibition against weed seeds	83
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. hirtum	Essential oil flowering stage	Grazing snail repellent effect	86
<i>Origanum x dolichosiphon</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial activity	87
P. H. Davis			
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Antimicrobial effect	88
<i>O. heracleoticum</i>	Essential oil	Antifungal	91
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial	99
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil of fresh leaves	High inhibitory effects on fusarium	100
<i>Oregano</i> turkey	Essential oil	Antimicrobial activity	102
<i>Oregano</i> turkey	Essential oil	Bacteriostatic and bactericidal effects	103
<i>Oregano</i> vulgare	Essential oil	Antibacterial	104
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Larvacidal against spodoptera littoralis	105
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Antimicrobial	106
<i>O. majorana</i> L.			
<i>O. vulgare</i> subsp. hirtum	Essential oil	Antigentoxic and antioxidant activity	107
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Antioxidant activity	108
subsp. glandulosum			
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Hot water extract	Phenolic content antioxidant properties	109
	Essential oil	Inhibited the growth of bacteria	
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Ovicidal and fumigant activity	110
<i>O. syriacum</i> L. var bevanii	Hexane, DCM extract	Antioxidant activity	111
	essential oil	Antimicrobial activity	
<i>O. heracleoticum</i>	Solvent extract	Antioxidants	114
<i>Coridothymus capitatus</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial activity	115
(Spanish <i>Oreganum</i>)			
<i>Thymus mastichina</i>			
(Spanish <i>O. majorana</i>)			
<i>O. vulgare</i>			
<i>O. saccatum</i> L.	Aerial part, essential oil	Antimicrobial	116
<i>O. onites</i> L.	Essential oil/extract	Scavenging activities and reducing/antioxidant	117
<i>O. majorana</i> ,	Essential oil	<i>In vitro</i> inhibitory activity	123
<i>O. onites</i> , <i>O. vulgare</i>			
<i>O. vulgare</i> L.	Essential oil	Antioxidant activities, scavenging activity	124
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Anti-inflammatory, antiseptic and antimycotic	126
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. ssp. hirtum	MeOH extract	Antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory	127
<i>O. compactum</i>	Ethanol, EtOAc extract	Anticancer, antimalarial, antioxidant activity	128
<i>O. glandulosum</i> (Desf.)	Essential oil	Insecticidal, grain protectant	129
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Aerial part EtOH extract	Radical scavenging activity	130
<i>O. onites</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial against <i>paenibacillus</i>	131
<i>O. vulgare</i> spp. hirtum	Essential oil	Antimicrobial and antioxidant	132
<i>O. vulgare</i> L. subsp. hirtum	Essential oil	Antimicrobial	143
(Link) Ietswaart			
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial	144
<i>O. minutiflorum</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial	146
<i>O. ehrenbergii</i> Boiss	Essential oil	Inhibited nitric oxide production	149
<i>O. syriacum</i> L.		Anti-inflammatory	
<i>O. vulgare</i>			

(contd.)

<i>Oregano vulgare</i> L. ssp. hirtum (Greek Oregano)	Ethanol extracts	Antioxidants	151
<i>O. syriacum</i> L.	Acetone extracts	Antimicrobial and antioxidant	153
<i>O. majorana</i>	Essential oil	Larvacidal	154
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Anthelmintic effect	155
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Antibacterial against salmonella enterica serovar typhimurium	156
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum	Essential oil	<i>In vitro</i> phytotoxic activity, antifungal activity, hemolytic activity	158
<i>O. vulgare</i> ssp. hirtum	Essential oil	Antifungal	160
<i>Origanum</i>	Essential oil	Antimicrobial	161
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Essential oil	Anticancer	162
<i>O. vulgare</i>	Extract in soyabean oil	Antioxidant	163

but also species from other genera with similar sensorial qualities are called 'Oregano'⁸. *Oregano* (*Origanum vulgare*) is a native herb of the Mediterranean countries, such as Italy and Spain, and is used as has been commonly used to treat diarrhea and pain as well as a spicy herb worldwide⁹. *Oregano* is of great economic importance due to its use as a spice and as an essential oil.

The *Oregano* essential oil is rich in phenolic compounds (e.g. rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid and other hydroxycinnamic acid compounds) and has strong antioxidant, antimicrobial, cytotoxic and antifungal activities^{10,11}. Due to all these beneficial effects on human health, *Oregano* essential oil is being used to extend the shelf life of foods¹². Many *Origanum* plants are characterized by a wide range of volatile secondary metabolites. By the existence of chemical differences with respect to both essential oil content and composition, *Origanum* plants are widely used in the flavoring of food products and alcoholic beverages, as well as in perfumery because of their spicy fragrance. Moreover, in particular, owing to the antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of their essential oils.

Origanum species have recently been of great interest in academia, the food industry and agriculture as potential natural additives to replace synthetic products¹³.

It has antifungal, antimicrobial, insecticidal and antioxidant activities¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Antispasmodic, antitumoral, antifungal and analgesic activities of *Origanum* sp. have been reported¹⁸⁻²¹. It is reported that *Origanum* has been used

as expectorant, antiparasitic, antihelminthic²² and for gastrointestinal complaints in Turkish folk medicine²³. *Origanum* sp. are also used as a carminative, diaphoretic, stimulant and tonic^{24,25} have suggested that carvacrol present in the essential oil of *Origanum* probably interferes in the release and/or synthesis of inflammatory mediators, such as the prostanooids and thus favour the healing process for gastric ulcers. Due to the antibacterial, antifungal, insecticidal, antioxidant, and anti-carcinogenic activities²⁶ the essential oil and its chemical composition of *Origanum* species is now being studied intensively²⁷⁻³¹.

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